

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Tackling the Autism and Assessment Support Crisis

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for addressing the autism and assessment support crisis

CotN_Autism_Report_1.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **There is a crisis in the diagnosis and support of autistic children and young people (CYP).** Two percent of CYP are autistic. They struggle to access diagnostic and support services.
- **There are systematic inequalities in diagnosis and support.** Girls, children from ethnic minority families and those from poorer families are particularly disadvantaged.
- **Life chances for autistic CYP are seriously harmed.** They can have poorer educational outcomes, higher rates of school exclusion and poorer health and life expectancy. Autistic CYP can have 30 years lower life expectancy.
- **Move from a diagnostic to a needs led system.** Early identification should be the norm. Meeting needs through effective support should not depend on diagnosis.
- **National level focus:**
 - Build education and health partnerships for assessing and supporting autistic children.
 - Develop/extend Continuing Professional Development (CPD).
 - Create local partnerships to lead a national strategy, targeted at the most disadvantaged wards, trialling data driven, community and family co-produced, “whole system” approaches.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Build effective local partnerships.
 - Share data and information.
 - Create diagnostic teams in schools.
 - Develop neurodiverse friendly school practices.
 - Develop CPD to support staff.
 - Build on the approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: There is a Crisis in Autism Support and Assessment

The current system fails autistic CYP and their families, and it fails society. We cannot keep doing more of the same...We need a radical overhaul of our approach to supporting autistic CYP and – most critically – to trial new approaches that better connect health and education.

“The number of autistic children seeking assessment has rocketed by 306% since Covid. We need to focus on the needs of autistic children rather than waiting for diagnosis before providing help.”

What you can do at a local level

- **Move from a diagnostic to a needs led approach.** Support should depend on a medical diagnosis but be baked into the way education, health and care settings work.
- **Build effective partnerships between education, health and social care professionals** for assessing and supporting children with autism.
- **Move to early identification and intervention strategies** to provide support at the point of need.
- **Develop data sharing systems** to support early identification and assessment of needs.
- **Provide and extend access to mandatory CPD courses for health, education, and social care professionals** to improve understanding and awareness of autism.
- **Build on but tailor to place the kinds of approaches featured below.**

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Neurodiverse schools	Create neurodiverse friendly practices. Examples include sensory friendly classrooms and flexible learning environments; ensuring calm transitions; removing visual clutter from classrooms; tailoring teaching to the needs of autistic CYP through low arousal teaching, providing short, clear instructions to autistic children, ensuring discipline processes take account of neurodiversity.	To build inclusive school environments that better support autistic CYP and their families; meet needs of autistic CYP and support successful educational and social outcomes.
Early Identification Use existing educational data e.g. Digitally Action Together as One (DATA1) project, Born in Bradford	Uses Early Years Foundation Stage Profile to support teachers in identifying children. Children with low total scores on the profile are 25 times more likely to receive a diagnosis of autism. In the DATA1 project, an autism specific sub score was calculated. Children who scored poorly on the autism-specific score were approximately 50 times more likely to receive a confirmed autism diagnosis, compared to children who did not receive a low score.	To support effective early assessment and intervention and lead to better support and provision for autistic CYP.
Assessment in schools by multi-disciplinary school assessment teams e.g. SUCCESS project	Establish multi-disciplinary teams in schools to conduct autism assessments for children identified as being at risk of undiagnosed autism (and other neurodevelopmental disorders). Local authorities have tailored early identification systems to their contexts e.g. Early Identification of Autism Project in Nottinghamshire.	To provide greater service access; reduced the likelihood of missed appointments; reduce service costs. SUCCESS trial suggests major long-term savings and reduced waiting times for autism assessment and support.
Oral Health Approaches e.g. The toothPASTE project	The toothPASTE project works with autistic CYP, their families, and healthcare professionals to co-design an oral health support package to prevent tooth decay. This condition affects one in four of all five year-olds in England and is the primary reason for hospital admissions. It costs over £50 million annually. Tooth decay leads to pain, problems with speech, sleep disruption, altered eating habits, and financial impact on families.	To improved oral health; reduce hospital admissions; reduce costs to the NHS; improve attendance of pupils; reduce disruption in education.
Psychoeducation for autistic CYP	This approach uses psychoeducational resources to teach an individual about their condition by providing support, information, and management skills.	To help autistic CYP build on their strengths; support advocacy; improve professional practice; and create inclusive environments.